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Effect of Isopropyl Alcohol on Autoxidation of S(IV) Catalysed by Cu(II) in Alkaline Medium

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Abstract

The kinetics of the Isopropyl alcohol inhibited Cu(II) catalysed autoxidation of S(IV) in phosphate buffer medium has been studied and based on the observed results, the following rate has been proposed. Rate constants and the order of reaction were calculated and the reaction was found to be pseudo-first order in all cases. The effects of pH and temperature are also studied. The value of apparent activation (E_a) energy was calculated graphically by Arrhenius equation. Based on the inhibition parameter, the reaction follows a free radical mechanism.

$$-d[S(IV)]/dt = (k_1 + k_2[Cu(II)]) [S(IV)] / (1 + B [Isopropyl alcohol])$$

Keywords: Kinetics; Autoxidation; Rate constant; Cu(II); Catalysis; Inhibition; Isopropyl alcohol

Introduction

Acid rain is accredited mainly to anthropogenic sulfur dioxide (SO_2), and to a lesser extent, due to nitrogen oxide (NO_x) emissions. The process of oxidative change of sulfur dioxide into sulfuric acid is a significant reason for environmental acid precipitation. Sulfur dioxide is less against ecological oxidation through different processes, including photochemical oxidation in the gaseous stage by O_3 and H_2O_2 , produced in the climate by photochemical reactions; oxidation caused by O_2 in the aqueous phase catalysed by dissolved trace metal ions and by suspended particulate matters. The effect of isopropyl alcohol (IPA) on the autoxidation of sulfur (IV) (SO_2 or S(IV)) in the presence of copper (II) (Cu(II)) as a catalyst in an alkaline medium has been a topic of interest in the field of environmental chemistry and industrial processes. The autoxidation of sulfur (IV) is a significant reaction in atmospheric and industrial chemistry, as it plays a crucial role in the formation of sulfuric acid and other sulfur compounds. This reaction, which occurs in the presence of oxygen, can be catalysed by transition metals, particularly Cu(II). Isopropyl alcohol, being an alcohol, is known to have potential effects on oxidation reactions due to its ability to interact with reactive intermediates, potentially modifying the rate and mechanism of the reaction. In the case of S(IV) autoxidation, IPA may influence the reaction pathway by altering the redox potential of Cu(II), providing a protective effect on the sulfur species, or by changing the solubility of the reactants in the medium (Shivaraj and Rajagopal, 2018). Studies have shown that alcohols like IPA can either inhibit or accelerate oxidation processes depending on their concentration and the specific conditions of the reaction (Lee and Wang, 2017). The presence of IPA may also affect the stability of the Cu(II) catalyst and alter the formation of sulfur oxides. Therefore, investigating the role of IPA in this system provides insight into the complex dynamics of catalysis, solvent effects, and oxidation mechanisms in aqueous alkaline medium.

Experimental

The experimental process followed the methods of Prasad et al. (1991) had previously stated. All chemical substances utilised were of analytical grade, and their solutions were prepared using double-distilled water. The reactions were carried out in 0.15-litre Erlenmeyer flasks, exposed to ambient air to facilitate the exchange of atmospheric oxygen. Each flask was situated within a beaker with an inlet at the lower part and an outlet at the upper part to enable the circulation of thermostatic water, maintaining the desired temperature at $33 \pm 0.1^\circ C$. The reaction was started by adding the desired volume of standard Na_2SO_3 solution for the reaction combination containing different added substances, like buffer and catalyst oxide. To allow for the ambient oxygen and

prevent the reaction from becoming oxygen mass exchange controlled, the reaction mixture was continually and magnetically agitated at 1600 ± 100 rpm. The kinetic studies were conducted in a buffered medium, maintaining a constant pH throughout the entire reaction process. For this purpose, a 10 cm^3 buffer medium of Na_2HPO_4 (0.08 mol dm^{-3}) and KH_2PO_4 (0.02 mol dm^{-3}) was used to create a basic alkaline medium with a total volume of 100 cm^3 , thus achieving the desired pH. As previously mentioned, the kinetics were monitored by regularly removing the aliquot samples and titrating the unreacted S(IV) iodometrically in a slightly acidic medium. The reproducibility of the replicate measurements was generally better than compared to $\pm 10\%$. All calculations were conducted using MS Excel (Hussain et al., 2018).

Product analysis

When the reaction was complete, the separation of Cu(II) was accomplished through filtration and the determination of Sulphate was estimated gravimetrically. This involved the precipitation of sulfate ions as BaSO_4 , using a standard procedure (Begam et al., 2018).

The product analysis revealed that, in every instance, the sulphate recovery was $98 \pm 2\%$, which is in agreement with eq. (1)

Results

Preliminary Investigation

In an alkaline medium, the kinetics of both uncatalyzed and Cu(II)-catalyzed reactions were examined in pH 7.30-9.40 and temperature 33°C . In both of the cases, the first-order dependence of S(IV) was observed. The $\log [\text{S(IV)}]$ versus time, t , was used to compute the first-order rate constant, k_1 which was shown in Fig.1, and it is observed that both the uncatalysed and Cu (II) catalysed autoxidation of S (IV) reaction are inhibited by isopropyl alcohol.

Fig. 1. The disappearance of S(IV) in suspensions saturated with air at $[\text{S(IV)}] = 2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ at pH = 7.30, $t = 33^\circ\text{C}$

Uncatalysed reaction

In this study, the reaction was examined without adding Cu(II). It is well known that the uncatalysed reaction is initiated due to the presence of trace metal particle impurities in the reagent samples and the distilled water utilized for the preparation of solutions.

Dependence of S (IV)

The dependency of the reaction rate on $[\text{S(IV)}]$ was calculated by changing sulphite in the range of $1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ to $9 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ at pH= 7.30, $t = 33^\circ\text{C}$ in phosphate buffer medium. The kinetics was found to be first order in $[\text{S(IV)}]$ as shown in Fig. 1 and $\log [\text{S(IV)}]$ versus time plots were linear. The values of the first-order rate constant, k_1 are shown in Table 1. The following rate law (2) describes how the reaction rate depends on $[\text{S(IV)}]$.

$$-d [\text{S(IV)}] / dt = k_1 [\text{S(IV)}] \quad (2)$$

Table 1. The values of k_1 for uncatalysed reaction at different $[S(IV)]$ at pH =7.30, $t=33^\circ\text{C}$ $\text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4=8\times 10^{-2}\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\text{KH}_2\text{PO}_4=2\times 10^{-2}\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

$[S(IV)] \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	$(10^3) k_1 \text{ s}^{-1}$
0.001	1.04
0.002	1.37
0.003	1.50
0.005	1.65
0.007	2.01
0.009	2.30

Isopropyl alcohol dependence

The dependence of Isopropyl alcohol (IPA) on the S(IV) autoxidation was studied by varying the [Isopropyl alcohol] from $1\times 10^{-6}\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ to $9\times 10^{-4}\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ in phosphate buffer medium at $[S(IV)]=3\times 10^{-3}\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, pH =7.30, $t=33^\circ\text{C}$ and observed that the rate of the reaction was decreased by increasing isopropyl alcohol. The results are given in Table 2. In the presence of isopropyl alcohol, the nature of the S(IV) dependence remained first order. According to the rate law (3), the first-order rate constant k_{inh} was defined in the presence of isopropyl alcohol.

$$-d[S(IV)]/dt = k_{inh}[S(IV)] \quad (3)$$

The values of k_{inh} at different [Isopropyl alcohol] are given in Table 2.

Table 2. The values of k_{inh} at different [Isopropyl alcohol] at $S(IV)= 3\times 10^{-3}\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, pH = 7.30, $t = 33^\circ\text{C}$, $\text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4=8\times 10^{-2}\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\text{KH}_2\text{PO}_4=2\times 10^{-2}\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

[Isopropyl alcohol] mol dm^{-3}	$10^3 K_{IPA} (\text{S}^{-1})$	$1/K_{IPA} (\text{S})$
1×10^{-6}	0.409	2445
3×10^{-6}	0.378	2646
7×10^{-6}	0.340	2941
1×10^{-5}	0.283	3534
3×10^{-5}	0.261	3831
5×10^{-5}	0.243	4115
7×10^{-5}	0.227	4405
9×10^{-5}	0.207	4831
1×10^{-4}	0.187	5348
3×10^{-4}	0.142	7042
5×10^{-4}	0.107	9346
7×10^{-4}	0.0877	11402

According to the rate law, the values of the first order rate constant k_{inh} in the presence of isopropyl alcohol dropped as [isopropyl alcohol] increased.

$$k_{inh} = k_1/(1+B[IPA]) \quad (4)$$

where B is the rate-inhibition parameter for isopropyl alcohol.

Rearranging the equation (4) yields

$$1/k_{inh} = 1/k_1 + B[IPA]/k_1 \quad (5)$$

According to equation (5), the plot of $1/k_{inh}$ v/s [Isopropyl alcohol] was found to be linear with positive intercept. The values of intercept ($1/k_1$) and slope (B/k_1) were found to be $3.2\times 10^3 \text{ s}$ and $1.2\times 10^7 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}$ at pH = 7.30, $t = 33^\circ\text{C}$ From these values the values of slope/Intercept give inhibition parameter B was found to be $3.6\times 10^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3$.

Fig. 2. Effect of Isopropyl alcohol at $[S(IV)] = 3\times 10^{-3}\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ pH=7.30 and temp= 33°C in Phosphate buffered medium

Cu(II) catalysed reaction

The kinetics of Cu(II) catalysed autoxidation of S(IV) was studied in alkaline medium in the absence of inhibitor Isopropyl alcohol.

[S(IV)] Variation

The dependence of S(IV) on reaction rate was studied by varying [S(IV)] from 1×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ to 9×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ at different but fixed Cu(II) concentrations of 2×10^{-5} , 4×10^{-5} and 6×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³ at pH = 7.30, t = 33°C. The kinetics was found to be first order in S(IV), and the plots of [S(IV)] v/s time are linear as shown in Fig. 1.

Cu(II) variations

The effect of Cu(II) on the reaction rate was studied by varying Cu(II) from 1×10^{-5} to 1×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³ at S(IV) = 2×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ pH = 7.30, t = 33°C in alkaline buffer medium. The values of the first-order rate constant k_{cat} for S(IV) oxidation were determined and are shown in fig 3. The two-term rate rule (6) was used to describe the nature of the dependency of k_{cat} on Cu(II).

$$-d[S(IV)]/dt = k_{cat}[S(IV)] = (k_1 + k_2[Cu(II)])[S(IV)] \quad (6)$$

$$\text{Or } k_{cat} = k_1 + k_2[Cu(II)] \quad (7)$$

From the plot in Fig. 3 the values of intercept is equal to k_1 , and slope is equal to k_2 were found to be 7.09×10^2 s and 4.39×10^6 mol⁻¹dm³ s at pH = 7.30, t = 33°C, in phosphate buffered medium.

Fig. 3. The dependence of Cu(II) concentration at [S(IV)] = 2×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ pH = 7.30, t = 33°C, in Phosphate buffered medium.

Variation of pH

pH variation is carried out in the pH range of 7.30 to 9.40 at fixed S(IV), Cu(II) and isopropyl alcohol and temperatures. The rate did not vary with varying pH, and it is constant found that the effect of [buffer] was examined by varying the concentration of both Na₂HPO₄ & KH₂PO₄. So that the ratio [Na₂HPO₄]/[KH₂PO₄] remained the same, pH remained fixed. The values showed that the rate of reaction was insensitive to the buffer concentration. The results are given in Table 3.

Table 3. Effect of pH at S(IV) = 3×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, Cu(II) = 2×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³, [Isopropyl alcohol] = 7×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³ t = 33°C Na₂HPO₄ = 8×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³, KH₂PO₄ = 2×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³

pH	$10^3 K (S^{-1})$
7.30	0.418
7.90	0.446
8.50	0.514
8.90	0.567
9.20	0.530
9.40	0.463

Rate law in the Presence of Isopropyl alcohol

A detailed study of the dependence of rate on S(IV), Cu(II) and pH within the presence of isopropyl alcohol revealed that the kinetics remain first order both in S(IV) and Cu(II) and the independence of pH obeys the following rate law.

$$-d[S(IV)]/dt = (k_1 + k_2[Cu(II)]) [S(IV)] / (1 + B [IPA]) \quad (8)$$

$$\text{Where } k_{inh} = (k_1 + k_2[Cu(II)]) / (1 + B [IPA]) = k_{cat} / (1 + B [IPA]) \quad (9)$$

$$1/k_{inh} = (1 + B [IPA]) / k_{cat} \quad (10)$$

$$1/k_{inh} = 1/k_{cat} + B [IPA] / k_{cat} \quad (11)$$

Table 4. The value of K_{inh} at different [Isopropyl alcohol], $S(IV) = 3 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $Cu(II) = 2 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $pH = 7.30$, $t = 33^\circ\text{C}$, $Na_2HPO_4 = 8 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $KH_2PO_4 = 2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

[Isopropyl alcohol] mol dm ⁻³	$10^3 K_{inh} \text{ (S}^{-1}\text{)}$	$1/K_{inh} \text{ (S)}$
1×10^{-6}	1.60	625
3×10^{-6}	1.50	667
7×10^{-6}	1.33	752
1×10^{-5}	1.18	847
3×10^{-5}	1.12	893
5×10^{-5}	1.05	952
7×10^{-5}	0.994	1006
9×10^{-5}	0.874	1144
1×10^{-4}	0.801	1248
3×10^{-4}	0.680	1470
5×10^{-4}	0.549	1821
7×10^{-4}	0.418	2392

Fig.4. Effect of [Isopropyl alcohol] at $S(IV) = 3 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ at $t = 33^\circ\text{C}$, $Cu(II) = 2 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $pH = 7.30$ in phosphate-buffered medium.

By plotting a graph between $1/k_{inh}$ versus [Isopropyl alcohol] gives a straight line with positive intercept Fig. 4. The values of intercept = $1/k_{cat}$ and slope = B/k_{cat} from the graph these values are found to be $8.0 \times 10^2 \text{ s}$ and $2.2 \times 10^6 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}$ separately. From these values, the value of the inhibition parameter B can be determined. Inhibition parameter $B = \text{slope/Intercept}$, that is $B = 2.7 \times 10^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3$.

Effect of temperature

K_{obs} values were calculated at various temperatures between 33°C and 43°C . Table 5 presents the findings. An apparent empirical energy of activation of $67.39 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ in the presence of isopropyl alcohol can be obtained by graphing $\log k_v/s$ vs $1/T$.

Discussion

In the experimental range of $pH = 7.30$ - 9.40 , the following equilibrium operates

In the pH range 7.30 to 9.40 , SO_3^{-2} is present predominantly. The reaction's rate shows that it is not affected by pH . According to Gupta et al. (2008), the radical mechanism is said to function in reactions when the inhibition parameters fall between 10^3 - 10^4 .

Table 5. The Effect of temp. On K_{obs} at $S(IV)=3\times 10^{-3}$ mol dm^{-3} , $Cu(II)=2\times 10^{-5}$ mol dm^{-3} , [Isopropyl alcohol] = 7×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3} , $Na_2HPO_4=8\times 10^{-2}$ mol dm^{-3} , $KH_2PO_4=2\times 10^{-2}$ mol dm^{-3}

Temp.	$10^3 K_{obs} (S^{-1})$
33°C	0.418
38°C	0.655
43°C	1.02

In the present study, the value of inhibition parameter for uncatalysed and Cu (II) catalysed autoxidation of S (IV) by isopropyl alcohol is found to be 3.6×10^3 & 2.7×10^3 mol⁻¹dm³ respectively. Based on the observed data, this also strongly supports the radical process in the current scenario (Begam et al., 2013; Hussain et al., 2018a; Hussain et al., 2018b; Hussain et al., 2018c; Begam et al., 2018; Sharma et al., 2018a; Sharma et al., 2018b) (eqs. 17-26):

In the mechanism, no role is assigned to O_2^{-} , which is also known to react with sulfur (IV) slowly (Manoj et al., 2000). It may be disproportionate to form H_2O_2 and O_2 or it may be scavenged by impurities. Using the steady state approximation and the long chain hypothesis $d[SO_3]/dt$, $[SO_4]/dt$, $d[SO_5]/dt$, to zero. It can be shown that the rate of initiation is equal to the rate of termination (eq. 27):

$$k_1[Cu(II)(SO_3^{-2})(O_2)] = \{k_7[X] + k_8[IPA]\} [SO_4^{-1}] \quad (27)$$

Since the reaction is completely stopped in the presence of $[IPA] = 1 \times 10^{-4}$ mol dm^{-3} , the steps (20) and (23) appear to be unimportant. The rate rule that follows can be derived from the mechanism mentioned above (eq. 28):

$$R_{cat} = k_1 [Cu(II)] [S(IV)] / \{k_7[x] + k_8[IPA]\} \quad (28)$$

We found similarities between the experimental rate of law and the calculated rate of law by comparing the two. The inhibition constant's computed value B is 3.6×10^3 mol⁻¹dm³, which is in the range of 10^3 - 10^4 . We therefore deduced that isopropyl alcohol functions as a free radical scavenger in Cu (II) catalyzed autoxidation of aqueous SO_2 in alkaline media, based on the computed value of B and, a free radical mechanism can work in this system (Gupta et al., 2008).

Conclusion

The findings of the isopropyl alcohol-inhibited Cu (II) catalyzed autoxidation of S(IV) indicate that the oxidation is inhibited with rapid influence. The current study's inhibition factor values for both

uncatalyzed and Cu(II) catalyzed autoxidation of S(IV) fall between 10^3 - 10^4 , indicating the presence of a free radical mechanism. This work highlights the potential of using organic additives like isopropyl alcohol to regulate undesirable oxidation reactions in aqueous systems, especially those relevant to atmospheric chemistry, water treatment and pollution control.

Future scope

The results are useful for modeling rainwater acidity and, therefore a great use of meteorology and impressive chemistry. This study is important in understanding the mechanism of the atmospheric oxidation of S(IV) by O_2 . The findings can be applied to environmental systems and industrial processes to control sulfur oxidation and understand pollutant behavior under varying alkaline conditions.

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Author Contributions

PS, HS and DSNP conceived the concept, wrote and approved the manuscript.

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Competing interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Ethics approval

Not applicable.

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